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A role for TOX and the exhaustion program in aging.

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Involvement of TOX in the aging process in humans was indicated by its characteristic, high expression in the newborn CD8+ T lymphocyte. LAG-3 and TIGIT instead defined the aged CD8+ T lymphocyte (CD8+ T-cells from older adults). Tox resides at the crux or vertex of what appears to be a critical component of the aging process derived from the blood.